

A review of cryogels synthesis, characterization and applications on the removal of heavy metals from aqueous solutions

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Abstract

The physical and chemical attributes of cryogels, such as the macroporosity, elasticity, water permeability and ease of chemical modifications has led to an expanding research interest in a variety of areas, such as water purification, cell separation, catalysis, regenerative medicine, biotechnology, bioremediation and biosensors. Cryogels have shown high removal efficiency and selectivity for heavy metals, nutrients, and toxic dyes from aqueous solutions but there are challenges when scaling up from lab to full-scale applications. This paper represents an overview on the most recent advancements in the use of cryogels for the removal of metal ions from water and attempts to deepen the understanding of the mechanisms involved. The review also describes the advantages of cryogels over other adsorbents and covers synthesis and characterization methods such as SEM/EDS, TEM, FT-IR, zeta potential measurements, porosimetry, swelling and mechanical properties.

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1. Introduction

Over the last century due to industrialization there has been a continuous increase of heavy metal contamination of water bodies. Among the several harmful water contaminants are heavy metals such as As(III), As(V), Cd(II), Cu(II), Ni(I), Pb(II), Zn(II) and Hg(II). Heavy metals are toxic and tend to accumulate in the food chain and can cause severe health problems [1,2]. Accumulation is enhanced by the tendency of heavy metals to form complexes with biological matter [3–5]. Ingestion of cadmium, arsenic, vanadium and lead above the tolerance levels have been linked to kidney [6–8], DNA damage [9,10], cancer [4,5,11], brain damage [4,12], obstructing of protein and oxidation of lipids, which lead to the development of cardiovascular diseases [7,13,14]. Table 1 shows the negative effects of heavy metals on human health and the maximum contaminant level (MCL) standards in drinking water set by the US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) [15] and European Union Drinking Water Directive [16] on the quality of water intended for human consumption.

The efficient removal of these toxic metal ions is a challenging task due to the high cost and complexity of treatment methods, which are highly dependent on the chemistry of the solutions. Several methods like membrane separations, ion exchange and adsorption [17,18], chemical precipitation [19,20], coagulation [21] and bioremediation have been used [22–24].

As alternatives to chemical precipitation and membrane filtration, ion exchange and adsorption can be used [25–29]. Adsorption has been considered the most suitable and applicable due to the simplicity of a process and cost-effectiveness. Modified natural materials (zeolites, activated carbons), industrial inorganic substances (coals, resins, silica), by-products (fly-ash), synthetic polymers (hydrogels, cryogels), or biopolymers have been used as potential adsorbents for heavy metal removal [30–35].

Cryogels is a variety of cryogenically-structured polymeric materials that have attracted the interest in various areas, such as medicine, biology, cell/tissue engineering, food technology, ecology, construction in permanent frost regions and others [36–44]. Cryogels are comprised of three-dimensional flexible polymeric structures synthesized via a freeze-thawing techniques [45–47]. The advantages of cryogels include a 3-D supra- and macroporous cross-linked matrix and chemical and structural stability [44,47–52]. Also, by using hydrophilic functional groups high water retention capacity can be achieved [49]. Cryogels are similar to ion-exchange resins in numerous regards; they are polymeric materials and employ electrostatic forces for the removal of ionic contaminants from water. However, compared to resins whose structures are robust, the cryogels structures are elastic and can retain substantially more water [53,54]. The presence of specific functional groups such as -OH, -NH₂, -SO₃H, -COOH, -CONH₂ in cryogels are enhancing the removal of water contaminants [29,55,56]. The contaminants can be adsorbed onto the external surface and in addition into the swollen 3D system of cryogels. Moreover, due to the biocompatibility properties of most types of cryogels [57–60] they can be used as an adsorbent to remove Fe(III) ions from blood plasma [57].

Cryogel properties can be acquired by controlling the synthesis conditions, such as the type of monomers, reaction time [61–63], temperature and ratio of precursors [64–67]. Cryogels with specific properties can be made by copolymerization of more than one type of monomer or by post-modification of the polymerized products via graft polymerization and other methods [27,52,54]. In addition to high adsorption capacity and wide modifiability, cryogels can be

regenerated by desorbing the pollutants and regaining the adsorption capacity in consecutive treatment cycles [55,68,69]. However, there are several issues that prevent the scale up from the lab-scale to pilot and practical commercial applications such as the recovery of cryogel after the adsorption process, selectivity and competitive adsorption in complex aqueous solutions [28,70,71] and stability problems which may cause structural collapse and prevent their reuse [60,69].

Most research articles and reviews on the use of cryogels point to the growing number of areas where cryogels are proposed for application, for example, in medicine [43,47,72–75] as tissue engineering scaffolds [76], drug delivery systems [77] or protein purification agents [78], ecological engineering for remediation of soil and water from dyes [79] and organic pollutants, in sensors [80] and supercapacitors applications [81,82]. However, to the best of our knowledge, there is not any review paper on the application of cryogels for the removal of heavy metals from water. In this paper a comprehensive presentation of the latest developments in cryogels synthesis, characterization techniques and applications on heavy metals from water are presented, including advances associated of cryogels over other materials, factors influencing and mechanisms of removal and cryogel reusability.

In the following, for simplicity the nomenclature of cryogels composition is based on their monomer(s) without mentioning cross-linking agents or other chemicals used. For example, a cryogel synthesized of glycidyl methacrylate monomer will be mentioned as p(GMA) and a copolymer cryogel consisting of GMA and histidine will be mentioned as p(GMA-co-His). For nanocomposite cryogels, the nano-sized constituent will appear following a slash mark, e.g., a nanocomposite of chitosan and dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate monomers doped with Fe nanoparticles will be mentioned as p(CHI-co-DMAEMA)/Fe.

2. Advantages of cryogels over other adsorbents

A variety of adsorbents such as lignin [83,84], tannin [85,86], chitin [87], chitosan, zeolite [88–90], clay, by-products of agricultural industry, activated carbon [91,92], carbon nanotubes [93,94] and synthetic polymer-based materials [95–97] have been used for adsorption of heavy metals from water. These materials are usually highly porous and the sorption process takes place on specific locations on the large surface area within the particles [31,35,98]. Adsorption is adhesion of substances to a surface. Depending on the interaction between the

adsorbent and the adsorbate, adsorption is classified as physical and chemical adsorption. Physical adsorption (physisorption) is a result of the attraction of a substance on the solid surface by van der Waals forces. Physical adsorption occurs as mono- or multi-layer and is reversible. Chemical adsorption (chemisorption) occurs when there is chemical interaction between functional groups on the solid surface and adsorbed substance. This type of adsorption is mono-layered and not reversible adsorption via electrostatic interactions of ions with oppositely charged groups [99]. Another mechanism of removal is the ion-exchange method based on the exchange of ions between the solution phase and the solid matrix. A combination of the above mechanisms may occur depending on the nature of the adsorbent and the adsorbate [100].

For porous adsorbents, the main property relevant to adsorption is the specific surface area, which determines the capacity of the material. Porous adsorbents such as activated carbons usually have a high surface area, from hundreds to thousands of m^2/g [34,101] while the surface area of cryogels is typically between 5-106 m^2/g [55,102–104] similar to natural zeolites and other aluminosilicate materials. However, the absence of a complex porous structure is advantageous when it comes to kinetics due to the absence of restrictions of diffusion in micropores. This might be very crucial for certain applications when a fast response is required. Also, cryogels have open-ended pores which contribute to the fast diffusion in contrast to the closed-end pores of conventional porous materials [57,58,105]. The relatively low surface area can be compensated with a high number of active sites distributed on the cryogel walls and also the adaptability of cryogels as the surface can be easily altered by adding functional groups and ligands, which can greatly contribute to the capacity and selectivity [26,47,52,57,60,71,106]. Moreover, hydrogels and cryogels have the ability to expand their structure due to their high swelling capacity [107,108]. Thus, they can absorb water very fast resulting in the rapid removal of toxic water spillages or small amounts of toxic water in soils. The rapid absorption of water enhances the removal of pollutants as the absorbed water brings them in contact the surface active sites [109–112].

Another advantage of cryogels is that they can be prepared in several different shapes like beads, sheets and columns (Fig. 1) [113–115]. This flexibility is highly desirable when the material is paced into filtering devices. Also, they can form composites with various materials, such as activated carbons [116–118], zeolites [119] and nanoparticles NPs [55,68,120,121] for acquiring several desired properties.

Due to highly macroporous structure with open pores up to hundreds of microns and interconnected flow channels, cryogels in the form of monoliths could be preferred as an adsorbent for the removal of pollutants even at high viscosity and high flow rates. With these structural features, the pollutants could easily transferred into the polymeric network without any limitations and backpressure [123]. For instance, Plieva et al. designed and prepared macroporous gel monoliths with embedded molecularly imprinted particles packed in the special plastic housings (Fig. 2) [113]. This plastic housing protects cryogels from mechanical attrition without any loss of adsorption properties and structural changes while special design on the gel increases the flow rate of the contaminated solutions [113].

3. Cryogels synthesis

Cryogels are described as a class of super porous spongy 3D network gel structure prepared via freeze-thawing method (Fig. 3). Due to the nature of used monomers, cryogels could be classified into cationic, anionic and amphoteric. Examples of some commonly used functional monomers include 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propansulfonic acid, acrylic acid, maleamic acid and methacrylic acid for anionic cryogels, while (3-acrylamidopropyl)trimethylammonium chloride, 2-(Dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate, allylamine, vinylamine, 4-vinylpyridine and 3-vinyl pyridine for cationic cryogels. Table 2 presents the most commonly used monomers in cryogels synthesis.

The freezing-thawing technique involves the free-radical copolymerization of a monomer and cross-linker in the presence of solvent such as water, dioxane and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), which is soluble in the monomer mixture and could be used as pore developer [144–147]. Cryogel preparation should be carefully tuned to ensure that the co-polymerization and formation of a 3D cross-linked polymeric network takes place after the formation of ice crystals is completed. Different lattice structure of crystals of solvent in the solid phase allows the design of different porosity architectures even under same concentration of monomers cross-linking agent and temperature. The selection of solvent determines the synthesis temperature, for instance when the cryogel has to be prepared at high temperature of -6 to +10 °C then 1,4-dioxane or DMSO can be used instead of water. After the radical polymerization is completed, the solvent is removed from the cryogel structure, leaving a porous structure within the highly cross-linked polymer network.

Cryogels are mainly synthesized by several cryotropic gelation techniques such as free-radical polymerization [148–151], irradiation (gamma-rays, electron beam, UV irradiation) [152,153], self-assembly based gel formation [154], polycondensation reaction under cryo-conditions (cross-linking of CHI or gelatin by dextran dialdehyde or glutaraldehyde (GA) [48,130,131], enzymatic catalysis [155], metal-polymer coordinated bonds or ionic interactions [131,156] (Fig. 4).

Free-radical polymerization is a commonly used technique and consists of three main stages: initiation, propagation, and termination [157,158]. In the initiation stage, free radicals (R^\bullet) are generated by the dissociation of an initiator (I) (dissociation):

where n is the number of free radical(s) produced. The polymerization reaction is initiated by methods such as using chemical initiators such as ammonium persulfate (APS) [159–163] or potassium persulphate (KPS) [52,164–166], potassium diperiodatocuprate [110], Ce^{4+} Isopropyl Alcohol Redox System [140], reduction of hydrogen peroxide or an alkyl hydrogen peroxide by iron (II) [167] and irradiation such as UV irradiation [168,169], photolysis of azoisobutyronitrile (AIBN) [170], gamma irradiation [171]. N,N,N,N-tetramethylethylenediamine (TEMED) [172–176] is often used to regulate the decomposition of persulfate at room or at subzero temperature and therefore accelerate the generation of radicals. The free radical then reacts with a molecule of monomer(s) (M) to produce the first radical M_n^\bullet (initiation):

Due to the very high reactivity of free radicals, they instantly attach the molecules of monomers, which lead to the growth of macroradicals (M_{n+1}^\bullet) (propagation):

Termination usually takes place by combination or disproportionation reactions. The combination is an increase in chain length due to the merging of two growing chains into one long (termination by combination):

In disproportionation reaction, a hydrogen atom from one chain end is subtracted and exchanged to another, resulting in a polymer with saturated end-group and another polymer with an unsaturated end-group (termination by disproportionation):

Depending on the type of termination, the final molecular weight of the polymer may differ: termination by combination gives a chain length that is twice as long as when termination goes by disproportionation [157,158]. Crosslinking is of great importance as it influences the structural properties of cryogels, their strength and swelling degree. Cryogels are crosslinked either physically or covalently to form networks [177–179]. Physical crosslinking happens through non-covalent interactions (hydrogen bonding, p-p interactions, Van der Waals and electrostatic interactions, metal coordination) [48,51,131,138], while chemical crosslinking is done by covalent interactions, which could be performed via a linker or zero-valent linkage applying carbodiimide/succinimide strategy or enzymatic cross-linking [155].

After completion of the polymerization reaction, cryogels are thawed at room temperature and washed with water to remove unreacted residual ingredients. The synthesized cryogel usually takes the shape of the container in which the polymerization occurred. The proportion of ingredients, freezing time (from 12 to 48 hours), temperature (from -12 to -18 °C) and the ratio of cross-linker to monomers mainly control the pores shape and size [111,182–184]. The formation of the macroporous structure takes place gradually as shown in Fig. 5.

Another two-step synthesis approach for cation exchange cryogels includes the cross-linking of premade polysuccinimide (PSI) by 1,4-diaminobutan or other bi-aminofunctional compounds in DMSO, which allows tuning the porosity of the material by varying the temperature of freezing from +8°C to sub-zero temperatures. Then, following hydrolysis of succinimide groups in mildly alkaline conditions carboxyl groups formation takes place, which are more flexible and accessible compared to carboxyl groups in cryogels from methacrylic or acrylic acid prepared in a conventional way. Despite the relatively high cost of cryogel preparation, these cryogels are potentially biocompatible and may be applied for the removal of toxic metals from biological fluids [185]. There are some studies on the use of an electron beam for initiation of radicals' formation but is too complex experimental setup. This method could be convenient for industrial production of sterile-grade cryogels for biomedical application [186]. Briefly, the initial monomeric mixtures are frozen to -20 °C for 2 h and then irradiated by applying a 10 MeV high-energy linear accelerator with a dose of 12 kGy in 3 kGy dose steps at a temperature of -12 to -15 °C. Ultimately, the cryogels are brought to room temperature, washed with water and freeze-dried [187]. Cryogels also can be prepared using UV initiated radical polymerization, where hydrogen peroxide or special UV initiators such as 4-benzoylbenzyl tri-

methyl-ammonium chloride [168,188]. For instance, frozen monomeric mixture was irradiated with full spectrum UV–Vis light by using a curing lamp with a power of 400 W for 2, 5 or 10 min [169]. The same method was used for the synthesis of a composite cryogel with embedded Ag NPs [169]. Finally, in addition to the preparation of cryogels using only synthetic ingredients, researchers have attempted to utilize natural raw materials, which are usually lower in cost and non-toxic. Elbarbary et al. synthesized a cationic p(CHI-co-HEMA) cryogel, in which chitosan was incorporated not only as a natural ingredient but also because of the presence of abundant functional groups [70]. Chitosan is a high molecular weight polysaccharide and a well-known adsorbent for heavy metals including noble metal anions [131,133]. While the amino groups in chitosan chains enable the adsorption of anionic pollutants, the adsorption of cationic pollutants takes place via the formation of polymer-metal coordination bonds.

Polymers and other materials can be used as a support for adsorbent particles or nanoparticles (NPs), i.e. forming nanocomposites [30,136,189,190]. Cryogels with specific functionalities can be prepared either by directly polymerizing a functional monomer or by modifying a polymerized product through secondary reactions and addition of several metal nanoparticles (Ag, Au, Pt, Pd, Fe, Al) [56,68,71,108,131,191]. For example, Jallilzadeh and Senel synthesized p(HEMA-co-MAH) cryogel modified by magnetite (Fe_3O_4) to improve sorption capacity of Cu(II) ions due to binding of these ions to magnetic nanoparticles and active sites of cryogel structure [55]. Onnby et al. synthesized composite p(AAm-co-D₃AAm)/Al₂O₃ cryogel by direct polymerization of Al NPs suspension in 6% solution of MBAAm:AAm with 1:7 molar ratio. The p(AAm-co-D₃AAm)/Al₂O₃ composite was used for the removal of arsenic (V) ions [68]. Suresh Kumar et al. fabricated iron-aluminium double hydroxides embedded in a cryogel by mixing Fe-Al particles with a monomeric solution to remove As(III) from water. Although iron and aluminium particles separately have often been used for arsenic removal, the co-precipitation of iron hydroxides and aluminium hydroxides increases the point of zero charge and the surface area of the adsorbent (see paragraph 3.4).

Another widely used method of synthesis of composite cryogels is a metal ion-imprinting technique, which is used for selective removal of metal ions. Principally, metal ions are interacting with the functional monomer(s) before polymerization reaction and then detached from the cryogel matrix. The produced voids in the polymeric network exhibit specific binding sites towards the metal ions used for ion-imprinting rendering them a highly selective adsorbent.

The preparation and use of ion-imprinting particles (IIP) such as metal ions in aqueous solutions have some difficulties because of multistep synthesis conditions, but the use of interaction between template and functional monomer could overcome this issue. Jallilzadeh and Senel used two-step synthesis method of preparation of p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Cu composite cryogel [55]. In the first step, MAH-Cu(II) pre-complex was fabricated by adding $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ to water containing MAH monomer to form MAH-Cu(II) prepolymerization complex. In the second step, cryogel template solution was prepared based on 50% HEMA. After polymerization p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Cu samples were incubated in $\text{Na}_2(\text{EDTA})$ solution to desorb the imprinted Cu(II) ions [55]. Tamahkar et al. prepared IIP cryogels using the same monomers but as a template ion was chosen Ni(II). In Fig. 6 presented a molecular structure of IIP cryogels with MAH monomer vs ion ratio 1:1 and 2:1 [192]. The interaction of Ni(II) ion with polymer goes by NH bond of the protonated imidazole ring of histidine moiety which is present in MAH monomer.

Tabakl et al. [123] synthesized p(HEMA-co-MAC)/IIP-Cd cryogels using a multistep approach. The HEMA-MAC-EGDMA composition toluene solution was co-polymerized at a temperature of 65 °C to 75 °C. The polymerized material was crushed to a fine powder and then saturated with Cd(II) ions. Afterwards, the material was utilized for fabrication of IIP cryogel according to the standard method [123]. The material was washed by Na_2EDTA solution to remove IIP to activate functional groups for targeted removal of Cd(II) ions from water. Onnby et al. synthesized molecular-imprinted polymer (MIP) by combining p(AAm-AA) cryogel with 4-phenylphenol, 2-VP, EGDMA with further imprinting with AsCl_3 for the removal of As(V) from water. Also to compare the removal capability authors modified p(AAm-AA) sample with free Al-NP and another p(AAm-AA) cryogel with SH functional groups from thiol-acetate precursor, namely p(AAm-AA)-SH [136].

4. Cryogels characterization techniques

4.1 Porosimetry and surface area

Nitrogen porosimetry technique is usually used for the determination of micro- and mesoporous structure of porous materials. The nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms are used with Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET), Density Functional Theory (DFT) and Barrett, Joyner, and Halenda (BJH) equations for the determination of the surface area, pore volume and pore size distribution [193]. Since polymeric cryogels by their nature are super-macroporous materials, of

the above equations only BET equation is used for determining the specific surface area due to the presence of micropores in the polymer walls [52,102,194–196]. Depending on the composition of the cryogel different degassing temperature and duration are used. As cryogels are polymeric materials mild degassing temperatures are used, typically less than 100°C [55,141] but in some cases higher temperatures up to 150°C were used [52,134]. The specific surface area values of some cryogels are presented in Table 3.

Some authors [201,202] used mercury porosimetry to determine the specific surface area of macroporous cryogels. However, the use of this method does not guarantee accurate data, since during the drying of cryogels for analysis on mercury porosimeter strong structural changes may occur and even complete destruction of the entire network of pores [47,74,203]. Also, since cryogels are made of soft matter during the intrusion/extrusion of mercury under high pressures the shrinking of the cryogels takes place, which will also affect the quality of the results.

4.2 FTIR characterization

One of the easiest and most useful characterization techniques for cryogels is FT-IR spectroscopy by which the several functional groups (e.g., -OH, -NH₂, -SO₃H, -COOH, -CONH₂) can be detected [29,49,59,142,191]. The most common functional groups found in cryogels and their characteristic wavelength ranges are shown in Table 4.

A characteristic FT-IR spectra of p(MAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) cryogel is shown in Fig. 7. The frequency at 3200 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the stretching vibration bands of -OH and N-H bonds, and the intra-hydrogen bond between them, the peak at approximately 3000 cm⁻¹ corresponds to -CH₂- and the stretching band of amide(II) and amide(III) groups are detected at 1620 and 1537 cm⁻¹, respectively. The spectra contain a stretching vibrations dissociated carboxyl group at 1213 cm⁻¹ and non-dissociated carboxylic groups at 1398 cm⁻¹, respectively [29]. Tekin et al. studied by FT-IR pristine p(HEMA) cryogel and after modification by VIM monomer and also p(HEMA-co-VIM) cryogel particles embedded into p(HEMA) cryogel.

Some more examples of cryogels FT-IR spectra are shown in Fig. 8. The p(HEMA) cryogel has a frequency at 3524 cm⁻¹ that corresponds to the vibration band of a hydroxyl group, an aliphatic C-H group at 2955 cm⁻¹, an ester band at 1262 cm⁻¹ and a frequency at 1728 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the carbonyl group. After the modification of VIM monomer, the hydroxyl group band became broader in both p(HEMA-co-VIM) and p(HEMA-co-VIM)/p(HEMA)

cryogels (Fig. 8 B,C). Also, the incorporation of the VIM monomer was observed by the new peaks at around 1535 cm^{-1} that corresponded to stretching vibration bands of imidazole ring (C-C/N-C stretching), 1249 cm^{-1} and 1570 cm^{-1} peaks of ring vibration and 1076 cm^{-1} of C-H bending group [52].

4.3 Zeta potential

The pH at which the adsorbent's surface charge is zero is called point of zero charge (pHPZC) [47,71,209]. When $\text{pH} < \text{pHPZC}$, the adsorbent acts as a positively charged surface while when $\text{pH} > \text{pHPZC}$, the adsorbent acts as a negatively charged surface [47]. Consequently, a cationic adsorbate has a higher affinity for the adsorbent when solution $\text{pH} > \text{pHPZC}$ and *vice versa* [191]. Another term that describes the electrokinetic phenomena is the isoelectric point. The isoelectric point (IEP) corresponds to the pH where the electrokinetic potential equals zero in the absence of specific adsorption on that surface [210]. In the absence of specific sorption on the surface of the material $\text{pHPZC} = \text{IEP}$. Usually, IEP is determined by using acidic and basic solutions by potentiometric and conductometric titrations [137,143] or using equipment for zeta potential calculation [29].

Baimenov et al determined the IEP of p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) cryogel from the electrokinetic data and found it in the pH around 4.1 (Fig. 9A) [29]. A cryogel having similar composition was studied by Tatykhanova et al. by potentiometric titration method. It was found that the IEP for p(AA-co-MAAc-co-AAm) cryogels were in the region of 4.0 to 4.3 [137]. The IEP of p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) indicate that the composition of cryogel is enriched by acidic monomer. It is known [211] that the value of the IEP depends on the acid/base ratio. Due to the higher activity of the MAAc monomer compared with AA and DMAAm precursor in radical copolymerization reaction the excess of the carboxylic groups were obtained and shift the position of IEP to the acidic pH.

Dragan et al. determined the pHPZC of p(CHI-co-VAm) cryogel before and after modification with (vinylbenzyl diethyl 2-hydroxyethyl) ammonium chloride functional groups. It was found that surface of parent cryogel had pseudo neutral behavior at pH around 5.5, while the introduction of additional functional groups of VBTACl shifts pHPZC by 0.6 units to pH 4.9 (Fig. 9B) [143]. Another example of amphoteric cryogels based on natural polymers as CHI and Gel cross-linked by oxidized dextran was studied by Akilbekova et al. and found that the IEPs of

Gel-OxD (1:1), (2:1) and (3:1) shifted from 7.0 for pure Gel to 4.59, 6.11 and 4.05, respectively [131].

4.4 Interaction of cryogels with water

4.4.1 Water permeability

Liquid permeability and flow rate of the solutions through cryogels are of the most important properties relevant to separation processes. Monolithic cryogel materials are reported as a promising filter for water treatment with a high liquid flow rate due to their interconnected macropores, allowing unhindered diffusion of solutes and mass transfer of substances [57,58,112,185,204,206]. The permeability strongly depends on the type of monomers, the ratio of cross-linker and the size of the cryogel column. The water flow rate of As(III) and Cr(VI) solutions synthesized by Andrabi et al. at lab scale filter of p(CHI-co-DMAEMA)/ Fe₃O₄ (2,5 cm in height and 1 cm in diameter) was 8 ml/min while the fabrication of a 6,5 cm height and 7 cm in diameter pilot filter had a flow rate of 85 ml/min [206]. Alkan studied the effect of flow rate though p(HEMA-MAH) cryogel used for the removal of Fe(III) ions (Fig. 10). They revealed that the adsorption capacity of the polymer decreases by 4 times with the increase of the flow rate of the solution from 0.5 to 4 ml/min [57]. The increase of the flow rate of a liquid negatively effects the removal efficiency of metal ions because of the decrease of contact time of ions with cryogel surface and reduces the filter service time [206]. Finally, Asir et al. observed the same phenomena when they treated human plasma for the removal of Cd(II) ions by an ion-imprinted cryogel. The adsorption capacity of p(HEMA-MAC)-IIP-Cd cryogel decreased significantly from 2.6 mg/g to 0.34 mg/g with the increase of the flow rate from 1 to 4 ml/min (Fig. 10) [185].

4.4.2 Swelling

Sahiner and Seven studied the swelling behavior of p(AMPS) hydrogels and cryogels [107]. From Fig. 11 it could be seen that cryogel reaches the maximum swelling capacity in 10 seconds, while hydrogel needs 8 h. It is obvious that even if the ratio of crosslinking is 100 times more than in synthesized hydrogels the swelling time of macroporous cryogel is 3600 folds shorter than conventional hydrogel. The fast swelling behavior provides many advantages in water purification [107].

The amount of water that a cryogel can adsorb depends on the chemical nature and concentration of monomers and partially on the crosslinking density. Generally, the higher the crosslinking degree, the lesser the swelling and adsorption capacity of cryogels [129,212,213]. For instance, during the synthesis of acrylic acid-based polymers an increase of the concentration of the crosslinking agent BisAAm from 7.37 to 14.36 % increases the density from 0.63 to 0.85 g/ml and lead to polymeric network structure loses and decrease of the swelling ratio from 287.37 to 9.57 [214]. Erdem et al. confirmed that the ratio of crosslinker and chain extender plays a significant role in the adsorption of metal ions (Fig. 12) [142]. It was found that an increase in the crosslinker ratio decreased the swelling capacity and limited the number of chelating groups. The maximum adsorption of Cu(II) was 115 mg/g and was obtained for 11.5% crosslinker and 30% chain extender [142].

The swelling of non-covalently cross-linked palladium metal-coordinating complex (MCCs) cryogel and ionic cryogels with gold complex in the solution with ionic strength of 1 M (pH 2.0-3.7) and 0.5 M at pH 2.8, respectively, resulted in complete dissolution of the material after few hours confirming the ionic nature of interactions [69,114]. At the same time, the cross-linked cryogels were stable in neutral and at pH above 3.5 (Fig. 13) [69]. The reason for the dissolution of cryogel is the shift of the dissociation equilibrium due to the suppression palladium-polymer complex. This occurred due to protonation of amino groups, which did not participate in coordination complex formation confirming the nature of coordination bond formation. MCCs soaked into 1 M of the solution of salt at pH 4.8 preserved its self-supported macroporous structure [133].

4.5 Optical and SEM/TEM microscopy

Optical microscopy imaging is the simplest technique for investigating the macroporosity of cryogels. In Fig. 14 the example of the macroporous structure of the p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) cryogel is shown.

In Fig. 14 SEM images of the p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) cryogel are shown indicating the interconnected macro-pores. The size distribution of interconnected pores was approximately in the range of 20–100 μm . The SEM imaging is often used for determination of the porous structure of the material however if materials were modified by different metallic nanoparticles the best technique is transmission electronic microscopy (TEM). For instance,

Onnby et al. proved the presence and size of Al NPs in the structure of the cryogel by TEM technique (Fig. 15) [68]. In Fig. 15 (b,c) at high magnifications individual agglomerates of crystalline Al NPs, appearing as black needle-like areas can be clearly observed. The TEM images of a modified p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) with Ag NPs is shown in Fig. 16 and as reveal that Ag NPs are spread evenly on the surface of the cryogel and have diameters between 10 and 20 nm.

4.6 Compression analysis

The balance between porosity and mechanical strength is a challenge and an important property of a macroporous cryogel. High porosity typically compromises the mechanical properties while the low porosity leads to mechanical imbalance and resistance to the passage of fluids and gases through the cryogel. The mechanical properties of cryogels are usually investigated by compression analysis done uniaxial stress (Young's modulus) exerted on the cryogels. Baimenov et al reported the mechanical properties of monolithic cryogel with 8 mm diameter and 15 mm height and determined that Young's modulus of fully swollen p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) sample was 9.18 ± 0.47 kPa [29]. The cryogel composition of 30/30/40 AMPS/AA/DMAAm had a Young's modulus of 3327 ± 31 Pa. A 50/50 mol% MAAc/DMAEMA cryogel with the same cross-linker ratio BisAAm/AAm 10:1 mol % and initial monomeric mixture concentration of 6% revealed higher Young's modulus of 53 and 914 kPa, which may be related to higher degree of electrostatic interactions between oppositely charged groups providing an additional physical cross-linking of the material. The stiffness of MCCs was estimated by varying concentrations of palladium and platinum complexes. The increase of the amount of the complexes concentration led to the increase of Young's modulus of MCCs. In order to avoid the gelation before crystallisation of water and to prepare a mechanically stable cryogel the concentration of $\text{Na}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ was in a range of 800 - 200 μM (Fig. 17) [215].

Berillo et al. comprehensively studied the change of Young's modulus for different pH and concentration of the cross-linking agent [215]. The decrease of acetic acid concentration from 0.2 M to 0.1 M in the reaction mixture of CHI and palladium (IV) complex led to the increase of gel formation rate, due to the decrease of non-frozen phase volume. As a result, at the same concentration of palladium complex, the efficiency of the cross-linking of CHI was increased. Therefore, the stiffness of MCCs prepared in the presence of 0.1 M was significantly

enhanced [215]. The relatively large value of Young's modulus (16.5 ± 0.1 kPa) for MCCs (Pd-0.8 mM in 0.1 M CH_3COOH) in comparison with 6.0 ± 1.5 kPa for MCCs (Pd-0.8 mM in 0.2 M CH_3COOH) can be explained by the high ligand exchange rate of palladium (IV) complex and sufficient acidic conditions [215].

The increase in the rigidity of the material is due to stronger and more rigid nanocomposite structure. High elasticity and good mechanical properties of materials give the possibility to use cryogels under various conditions and enhancing the reusability of the cryogels as adsorbents. Berillo et al. reported that even non-chemically cross-linked cryogels based on chitosan and gold complex concentrations of 0.2-4 mM revealed comparable to covalently cross-linked elasticity of 1.03-6.7 kPa, respectively. In the same study, it was illustrated that the prolongation of the incubation of samples in the frozen state leads to increase of Young's modulus, which is related to the low concentration of ligand and slow ligand exchange process [133]. Chemically cross-linked chitosan-based composite cryogels with Au NPs with concentrations of 1-4 mM exhibited Young's modulus of 41.5 - 50.4 kPa [25]. As expected the increase of metal complex concentration led to the improvement of mechanical properties. The control and optimized by diaminoethane p(Jeff600-co-GA) cryogels (height and diameter 5 x 7 mm) compressed to 70% had Young's modulus of 0.08 and 0.32 kPa, respectively [25]. It was shown that the incorporation of diaminoethane to the p(Jeff600-co-GA) cross-linked by GA increases Young's modulus value for cryogel due to an increase of the length of the polymer chain. Loo et al [216] compared Young's modulus of p(SA) and p(SA)-Ag NPs cryogels with Ag content of 167 mg/g. It was shown that modification of cryogels increases Young's modulus from 2.6 to 3.2 kPa. Savina et al. studied the mechanical properties of p(HEMA-co-PEGDA) cryogel and composite cryogels (p(HEMA-co-PEGDA)/ Fe_2O_3) and (p(HEMA-co-PEGDA)/ Fe_3O_4) (height and diameter 10x10 mm) compressed up to 85 % with a maximum loading of 18 N and found that no structure deformation takes place. Young's modulus for p(HEMA-co-PEGDA) was 16.4 ± 1.9 kPa, while the composite p(HEMA-co-PEGDA)/ Fe_2O_3 and p(HEMA-co-PEGDA)/ Fe_3O_4 cryogels was equal to 46.8 ± 4.9 kPa and 57.6 ± 10.8 kPa, respectively [189]. Shu et al. demonstrated that the immobilization of titanium dioxide (TiO_2) nanopowder ($d < 25$ nm) into the structure of a cryogel enhanced its flexibility and compressive strength. The initial p(AAM) cryogel (height diameter and 10x10 mm) had a Young's modulus

of 36.23 ± 0.82 kPa, while the TiO_2 impregnated cryogel had a Young's modulus equal to 44.48 ± 1.21 kPa [121].

5. Adsorption of heavy metals by cryogels

5.1 Overview

An overview of the published studies on the removal of heavy metals by cryogels is given in Table 5.

Tekin et al. synthesized p(HEMA-co-VIM)/p(HEMA) composite cryogel by embedding p(HEMA-VIM) particles prepared with suspension polymerization into p(HEMA) cryogel. The maximum adsorption capacity of the composite cryogel were 7.6 mg/g for Pb(II), 5.8 mg/g for Cd(II), 4.3 mg/g for Zn(II) and 2.5 mg/g for Cu(II) [52]. A (CHI-co-HEMA) cryogel achieved loading of 48.7 mg/g for Ca(II), 66.3 mg/g for Cu(II) and 57.6 mg/g for Zn(II) mainly by chemical chelation with functional groups of the cryogel [70]. Cimen et al. used synthesized poly-L-histidine immobilized poly(glycidyl methacrylate) (GMA) cryogel discs for the removal of Pb(II), Cd(II), Zn(II) and Cu(II) from aqueous solutions. The maximum adsorption capacity of heavy metal ions of p(His-co-GMA) cryogel discs were 6.9 mg/g for Pb(II), 6.4 mg/g for Cd(II), 5.6 mg/g for Cu(II) and 4.3 mg/g for Zn(II) [106]. Tatykhanova et al. reported the results of the adsorption of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) on amphoteric cryogels p(AA-co-MAAc-AAm). The p(AA-co-MAAc-AAm) composition was 55.5% of -COOH group and 44.5 % of -NH₂ group determined by potentiometric titration. The amphoteric cryogel removed up to 630 mg/g of Cu(II), 590 mg/g of Co(II) and 580 mg/g of Ni(II) at initial metals concentration of 63, 59 and 58 mg/L, respectively at pH=4. The interconnected macropores and spongy-like structure make these cryogels promising materials for water treatment [137,223]. To improve the sorption capacity of heavy metals, cryogels can be modified by various nanoparticles. Suresh Kumar et al. modified p(AAm) cryogels by iron and aluminium oxide to enhance removal of As(III) and As(V) ions from water. Results of extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS) indicated that As(III) forms a mononuclear complex with iron ions, while As(V) bounds with Al ions in binuclear complex or with mononuclear Fe ions. The maximum adsorption capacity of p(AAm)/Fe(OH)₃-Al(OH)₃ was 82.3 and 39.6 mg As/g for As(III) and As(V), respectively [220]. Composite cryogels with TiO_2 nanoparticles were studied by Onnby et al. [71] and Shu et al. [121]. Onnby et al. revealed that p(AAm) cryogel with embedded TiO_2 nanoparticles has higher

removal capability for Cu(II) compared to free TiO₂ suspension, 12.01 and 8.98 mg/g, respectively [71]. Shu et al. used the same monomeric mixture with different loading of TiO₂ nanoparticles for targeted removal of Pb(II) ions from aqueous solutions. Composite p(AAm) cryogel with 6% of TiO₂ showed equilibrium adsorption capacity of 23.3 mg Pb(II)/g TiO₂ while the free suspension of TiO₂ NPs was achieved 22 mg Pb(II)/g TiO₂ [121].

To improve the selectivity and adsorption capacity, ion imprinted polymer (IIP) modification can be applied. Tabakli et al. synthesized Cd-IIP cryogels and non-ion imprinted samples (NIP) by free-radical polymerization of HEMA and MAC monomers. The experimental results showed that although miniscule the ion-imprinted p(HEMA-co-MAC)/IIP-Cd sample were able to remove approximately two times higher of cadmium ions rather than the non-modified one, 32.2 µg/g to 16.3 µg/g, respectively [123]. Jallilzadeh et al. synthesized p(HEMA-co-MAH)/Cu(II)-IIP cryogels and modified them with Fe₂O₃ for effective removal of Cu(II) from aqueous solutions [55]. It was shown that not only ion imprinting but also magnetic nanoparticles could improve the adsorption capacity. The amount of removed Cu(II) ions by non-magnetic-IIP cryogels was 77.2 mg/g while the magnetic-IIP cryogel achieved a capacity of 182.7 mg/g. The p(CHI-co-HEMA) cryogel reached a capacity of 48.7 mg/g for Ca(II), 66.3 mg/g for Cu(II) and 57.6 mg/g for Zn(II) mainly by chemical chelation with functional groups of the cryogel.

5.2. Heavy metals removal mechanism on cryogels

Understanding the mechanism of adsorption is very important for further investigating the process of heavy metals removal onto different adsorbents; however, the elucidation of removal mechanisms of heavy metals on cryogels is a challenging task and literature is frequently approach the subject superficially. Different adsorption mechanisms such as physisorption, including electrostatic interaction and attraction by van der Waals forces, chemical sorption as chelation, metal coordination (Fig. 18) and complexation (Fig. 18) and ion-exchange (Fig. 19) or a combination of several of these mechanisms have been discussed in the literature could be found in the literature [31,137,224,225].

The adsorption mechanism of heavy metals onto the macroporous polymers depends on the chemical composition of the materials and typically involves more than one mechanisms [226]. The selective sorption on polymers toward heavy metals ions is influenced by several

factors relevant to the physicochemical properties of the surfaces including the functional groups, chelating agents, surface charge and active components as nanoparticles. Surface functional groups reactions are the dominant factor when it comes to selectivity and capacity [27,57,59]. For instance, amino-functionalized materials are effective for the removal of both anionic and cationic species of metals; the elimination of anionic species is achieved via electrostatic interaction [133], ion exchange or hydrogen bonding [54,192,227], whereas the removal of the cationic species is achieved via coordination with the amino groups [131].

Erol and Uzun synthesized PEI modified p(HEMA-GMA) cryogel via co-polymerization with methacryloyl benzotriazole to prepare Cu-IIP cryogel [103]. PEI ligand attracted the Cu(II) ions but the process was strongly depended on pH of the solution because of precipitation of Cu(II) ions as hydroxides at alkaline environment and the negative effects of acidic environment on the coordinate covalent interaction [103]. Tatykhanova et al. discussed more the removal mechanisms of synthesized amphoteric cryogels based on acrylic acid and allylamine [137]. Acrylic acid and methacrylic acid monomers have carboxyl functional groups, while allylamine has amine groups. The pK_a of the carboxyl group of acrylic acid and methacrylic acid is about 4.26 and 4.88, respectively and this $-NH_2$ group is 5.44. At pH values higher than the pK_a , carboxyl groups are ionized so these monomers can attract cationic metal species through electrostatic interactions. Also, oxygen atoms of carboxyl groups can donate paired electrons to cations and form complexes. Possible reaction paths of metal ions with carboxylic groups via ion-exchange of H^+ followed by chelation are shown in Fig. 20.

Tatykhanova et al state that Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions form coordination and ionic bonds between metal ions and amine and/or carboxylic groups of cryogels when aqueous solutions of metal salts pass through the gel specimen [137]. Cimen et al. found that synthesized p(GMA-co-His) cryogel has high adsorption capacity for cationic metal ions at pH 5.0–5.5. The removal depended on the nature of the imidazole ring of a poly-L-histidine ligand, which has a pK_a value of 6.05. Under these pH values, it is positively charged and repulsion between ligand and metal ions occurred. At higher pH the metal ions precipitation and competition with $-OH$ ions may cause a decrease in adsorption capacity [106].

Tekin et al. prepared a composite p(HEMA) cryogel containing p(HEMA-co-VIM) particles for removal of Pb(II), Cd(II), Zn(II) and Cu(II) ions from aqueous solutions and found that adsorption mechanism was covalent bonding. VIM monomer has imidazole moiety, a

heterocyclic aromatic compound having two nitrogen atoms in the ring. Because of Lewis base character of the nitrogen atoms in the hetero-aromatic ring, the imidazole group can easily make coordinated covalent bonds with transition metal ions by means of the N atoms [52]. The synthesized composite cryogel monoliths based on p(HEMA-GMA) and p(HEMA-BisAAM) were treated with 0.5M carbonate buffer for further modification with polyethyleneimine (PEI) or diethylaminoethyl (DEAE) [141]. This method allows the modification of the surface of the cryogel allowing rapid ion exchange kinetics. HEMA based cryogel has a neutral structure and do not participate in adsorption and therefore provides mostly mechanical strength. It is worth mentioning that attachment of PEI to p(HEMA-GMA) takes place due to the opening of epoxy ring, whereas for p(HEMA-BisAAM) cryogels most probably partial hydrolysis of the ester to carboxyl groups takes place and therefore only electrostatic interactions with PEI occur. This method of immobilization is applicable for the separation of large macromolecules (proteins, HSA, BSA), which cannot penetrate via the 3D polymeric network.

5.3. The effect of pH on adsorption

The adsorption process depends on solution pH because it affects the surface properties of cryogels as well as the speciation of ions in the aqueous phase. The investigation of the effect of solution pH on the removal of pollutants is described on the example of jeffamine-based cryogels p(Jeff600-co-GA-co-DAH) in Fig. 21.

The pH effect is an important factor for heavy metal adsorption from the aqueous phase, as some metals, like Cu(II) ion in the aqueous phase, can be found in various soluble and less soluble ionic forms due to hydrolysis. At basic and neutral pH higher than 5, Cu(II) ions precipitate as insoluble $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ while at pH range between 3 and 5 copper ions are dominant in Cu(II) and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$ ionic species (Fig. 22) [142,209]. The Cu(II) ion uptake was strongly pH-dependent as depicted in Fig. 20. The slight increase in pH after contact with the cryogel was due to the amino groups on the surface of the cryogel [142]. Adsorption of Cu(II) ions by the cryogel increased with increasing pH. The maximum equilibrium adsorption capacity value for Cu(II) ions at pH 5.5 was 118 mg/g. At $\text{pH} < 5.5$, Cu(II) ions were present as the dominant species leading to lower adsorption at low pH attributed to the competition between H^+ and Cu(II) ions. As the pH of the solution increased, the number of protons reduced from the functional groups on the surface of the cryogel leading to the formation of more metal/cryogel complexes [142].

Due to the increase of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ species at $\text{pH} > 5.5$ adsorption decreased which demonstrates lower attraction towards the cryogel surface.

Tekin et al. studied $p(\text{HEMA-co-VIM})/p(\text{HEMA})$ cryogels for the removal of $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ metals at different pH [52]. It was found that the adsorption capacity of cryogels at pH 3 was in the range of 2-8 mg/g and at pH 4 increased by 5 times. Jalilzadeh et al. investigated $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ ions removal by cryogel at pH range 3-6. The increase of adsorption capacity from 2 to 8 mg/g at pH 6.0 was due to the deprotonation of the functional imidazole ring of MAH causing enhanced Lewis base character [55]. Deprotonation also reduced the possible repulsive interactions between metal ions and protonated amino groups. To confirm the effect of pH on the adsorption of Pb to the thiourea-functionalized $p(\text{AA-co-DMAAm-co-AAc})$ cryogel, Kim et al studied the $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$ adsorption at initial concentration of 200 mg/L and pH values of 3–7. The amount of $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$ adsorbed tended to increase with increasing pH due to the interaction between the carboxylic acid group and metal ions which becomes stronger. The maximum adsorption amount was observed at pH 7. When the pH was higher than 7, the $\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$ precipitate formed making it difficult to accurately measure the adsorbed amount [102]. Composite cryogels based on crosslinked polyvinilamine or chitosan and porous strong base anion exchangers having (vinylbenzyl diethyl 2-hydroxyethyl)ammonium chloride functional groups, exhibited good adsorption capacity for $\text{Cr}(\text{VI})$ in the range of 200–320 mg/g in a pH range from 3 to 6 and drastically decreased at higher pH due to the deprotonation of amino groups of CHI and VAm [143].

5.4. Regeneration and reusability of cryogels

The two most important requirements for the reuse of cryogels are reversible adsorption and the chemical and/or physical stability of the material. Cryogels should be resistant to the typical environmental conditions, chemically and physically stable and resistant to microbiological degradation upon consecutive adsorption-desorption processes. The efficiency of regeneration and reuse of cryogels is shown in Table 6. Several aspects of regeneration, such as the choice of an effective regeneration solution, its type and concentration, the optimum time and volume of regeneration have not been systematically studied. A good regeneration solution should be inexpensive, relatively non-toxic, and simple in preparation and storage. The main solutions for regeneration are usually acids and/or bases, some of which are listed in Table 5.

Erdem et al. showed that only 3 regeneration cycles are possible for p(Jeff600-co-GA) as it significantly loses its adsorption capacity. They achieved only 56% of the recovery, which is most probably related to precipitation of copper hydroxide on the surface of the material. A more effective regeneration solution would be a solution of hydrochloric acid achieving nearly 100% of metal recovery due to complete protonation of amino groups. Jallilzadeh et al. used $\text{Na}_2(\text{EDTA})$ as desorption agent to regenerate Fe-IIP and noncomposite cryogels after adsorption of Cu(II) ions. Chemical analysis confirmed that after three adsorption-desorption cycles there were not any iron release and desorption of Cu(II) ions was over 96% in all cases [55]. Cimen et al. synthesized a p(GMA-co-His) cryogel, which revealed fast removal of Pb(II), Cd(II), Zn(II) and Cu(II) from aqueous solutions. Cryogel was regenerated using 0.1 M HNO_3 , and after five cycles of adsorption-desorption the regeneration ratio was at the level of 97% for all examined metals that indicate the reusability of proposed adsorbents [106]. Erdem et al. synthesized jeffamine (α,ω-diamino terminated polyoxypropylene-block-polyoxyethylene-block-polyoxypropylene) based cryogels p(Jeff600-co-GA), p(Jeff900-co-GA) and p(Jeff2003-co-GA) and cross-linked with polyoxypropylene tri-amine) for removal of Cu(II) ions and investigated the regeneration by NaOH solution and reusability of cryogels. It was shown that the higher the molecular weight of the monomer, which consequently has more ether functional groups (unpaired oxygen), and less amino groups result in better recovery for p(Jeff600-co-GA), p(Jeff900-co-GA) and p(Jeff2003-co-GA) reaching 56.3%, 61.5% and 69.2% recovery, respectively [25]. Non-desorbed Cu(II) at alkaline conditions most likely precipitated as copper hydroxide on the cryogel surface, or lead formation of coordination bonds with a non-protonated amino group, and as a result, the purification degree was reduced. Reusability results of ion-imprinted p(HEMA-co-MAC)/IIP-Cd and non-ion imprinted p(HEMA-co-MAC) cryogels showed that after 10 cycles of adsorption-desorption of Cd(II) ions cryogel samples retained 84.1 and 74.4 % of the maximum adsorption capacity, respectively [123].

6. Conclusions

The adsorbents based on hydrogels and cryogels are relatively new and promising and a review on this subject is timely. This review summarized and discussed the synthesis methods, characterization techniques and application of cryogels on the removal of heavy metals from aqueous solutions. Although relatively expensive in comparison to conventional adsorbents,

cryogels exhibit several advantages, such as the rapid kinetics and permeability, which could be of crucial importance in several applications. The literature review reveals that most of the reported cryogels and their modified forms possess high adsorption capacity for a variety of heavy metals under up to hundreds mg/g exhibiting particularly fast kinetics. The review attempts to deepen the understanding and fill the gap in the literature on the removal mechanisms, which strongly depend on the initial monomer composition and post-modification agent precursor. Even though cryogels have shown improved adsorption efficiency, they still face limitations when it comes to a large scale application, such as low mechanical strength under certain conditions. Therefore, it is essential to identify new cryogel composites with the appropriate physical and chemical properties capable of comprehensive metal species adsorption from aqueous media.

Acknowledgements

This work has been financially supported by the HORIZON 2020 projects “*Nanoporous and Nanostructured Materials for Medical Applications (NanoMed)*”, H2020-MSCA-RISE-2016, 734641, and the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellowship "Cryobacteria reactor" grant agreement N 701289, funded by the European Commission.

Appendix A. Nomenclature

4-VP - 4-vinylpyridine	K_F - Freundlich adsorption constant (mg/g)(L/mg)
AA - allylamine	K_L - Langmuir adsorption constant (L/mg)
AAc - acrylic acid	KPS - potassium persulphate
AdeM – adeninemethacrylate	MAAc - methacrylic acid
AgNP – silver nanoparticles	MAC - N-methacryloyl-L-cysteine
AMPS - 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propansulfonic acid	MAH - N-methacryloyl-l-histidine
APS - ammonium persulfate	MALA - maleamic acid
AIBN - azoisobutyronitrile	MAPA - N-methacryloyl-(L)-phenylalanine
AAM - acrylamide	MIP – molecular imprinted polymer
AN - acrylonitrile	MMCs - metal-polymer coordinated complex
APTACl - (3-acrylamidopropyl)-trimethylammonium chloride	MCL - maximum contaminant level
A_T - Temkin adsorption potential (L/mg)	n - Freundlich constant
BisAAM - N,N-methylenebis(acrylamide)	$Na_2(EDTA)$ - Ethylenedinitrilotetraacetic acid disodium

B_t - Temkin constant (J/mol)	salt
CMC – carboxymethyl cellulose	NHS - N-hydroxysuccinimide
C_e - concentration of adsorbate at equilibrium (mg/L)	NIPA - N-isopropylacrylamide
CHI – chitosan	NPs - nanoparticles
C_o - initial concentration of adsorbate (mg/L)	OxD – oxidized dextran
D ₃ AAM – D ₃ -acrylamide	P2 - pseudo 2nd-order kinetic rate constant (g/mg min)
DAH- diamino hexane	PEI - polyethylenimine
DEAE - diethylaminoethyl	PEGDA- polyethylene (glycol) Diacrylate
	PEGMA - poly(ethylene glycol) methyl ether methacrylate
DMAAm - N,N-Dimethylacrylamide	pHPZC - point of zero charge
DMAEMA- dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate	PVA – polyvinyl alcohol
DMSO - Dimethyl sulfoxide	PSI - polysuccinimide
EDC - 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide	q_e - amount adsorbed at equilibrium (mg/g)
EGDMA - ethylene glycol dimethacrylate	R^2 - correlation coefficient
HA - hydroxyapatite	SA - sodium acrylate
HEMA - 2-Hydroxyethyl methacrylate	SEM – scanning electron microscopy
His - histidine	T - temperature (°C)
FTIR - Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy	t - time (min)
GA – glutaraldehyde	TEMED - N,N,N,N-tetramethylethylenediamine
Gel - gelatin	ThU - thiourea
GMA- glycidyl methacrylate	TMP - 1,1,3,3-tetramethylpropane
Jeff 600– jeffamine ED600 (O,O'-Bis(2-aminopropyl) polypropylene glycol-block-polyethylene glycol-block-polypropylene glycol)	VAm - vinyl amine
MIM - 5-methyl-4-imidazolylmethanol hydrochloride	VIM - N-vinyl imidazole
IEP – isoelectric point	VBTAcl - (Vinylbenzyl)trimethylammonium chloride
IIP – ion imprinted polymer	Q-NFC - quaternized nanofibrillated cellulose

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Table 1

The MCL standards for the most hazardous heavy metals.

Heavy metal	Toxicity	US EPA MCL (mg/L)	EU MCL (mg/L)
Arsenic	Skin manifestations, visceral cancers, vascular disease	0.01	0.01
Cadmium	Kidney damage, renal disorder, human carcinogen	0.005	0.005
Chromium	Headache, diarrhoea, nausea, vomiting, carcinogenic	0.1	0.05
Copper	Liver damage, Wilson disease, insomnia	1.3	2.0
Lead	Damage the fetal brain, diseases of the kidneys, circulatory and nervous system	0.015	0.01
Mercury	Rheumatoid arthritis, and diseases of the kidneys, circulatory system, and nervous system	0.002	0.001

Table 2

List of monomers used in the cryogels synthesis (acronym in parenthesis)

Monomer	Structure	Functional group(s)	Ref.
2-Hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA)		Hydroxyl, vinyl group and ester groups	[26,57,70]

Poly(ethylene glycol methyl ether methacrylate) (PEGMA)		Ether and vinyl groups [125,126]
Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)		Hydroxyl group [45,127]
Gelatin and collagen		Carboxyl, amino, hydroxyl and amide groups [41,128,129]
Oxidized dextran or dextran dialdehyde (OxD)		Carbonyl, hydroxyl and ether groups [48,130,131]
Methacrylic acid (MAAc)		Carboxyl and vinyl groups [126,132]
Chitosan (CHI)		Primary amino, amide, ether and hydroxyl groups [60,131,133]
Ethylenglycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA)		Ester and vinyl groups [56,107-109,123,134-136]
N,N'-Methylenebis-(acrylamide) (BisAAM)		amide and vinyl groups [55,106]

2-Acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propan sulfonic acid (AMPS)		Sulfogroup, amide and vinyl groups [105,123]
Allylamine (AA)		Primary aminogroup and vinyl group [137,138]
2-(Dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate (DMAEMA)		Tertiary aminogroup and vinyl group [137,138]
N,N-dimethyl acrylamide (DMAAm)		Carboxyl amide and vinyl groups [29]
Glycidylmethacrylate (GMA)		Vinyl group, ester and epoxy groups [103,106]
(3-acrylamidopropyl)-trimethylammonium chloride (APTACl)		Amide, quaternary aminogroup, and vinyl group [139]
Jeffamine ED600 (Jeff600)		Amine and carboxyl groups [25]
4-vinylpyridine (4-VP)		Vinyl group and pyridine [136]

1-vilylimidazole (VIM)		Vinyl group and imidazole group	[52]
Glutaraldehyde (GA)		carbonyl groups	[48,130,131]
N-methacryloyl-L-histidine (MAH)		Amino, imidazole and ester groups	[55]
Acrylonitrile (AN)		Nitrile and Vinyl groups	[140]
Acrylamide (AAM)		Carboxyl, amine and vinyl groups	[136]
Polyethylenimine (PEI)		Primary, Secondary and amine groups	[141]
Diamino hexane (DAH)		Primary amine group	[142]
N-methacryloyl-L-cysteine (MAC)		Thiol, amide and carboxyl groups	[123]
Vinylamine (VAm)		Vinyl and primary amine groups	[143]

Table 3

Specific surface area of cryogel materials

Cryogel	S _{BET} (m ² /g)	Reference
P(HEMA-co-VIM)	39.7	[52]
P(HEMA-co-VIM)/p(HEMA)	78.6	[52]
p(HEMA-co-MAH)	18.6	[55]
p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Cu	43.4	[55]
p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Cu-Fe203	106	[55]
p(AA-co-MA-co-AAc)	21.9	[102]
p(AA-co-MA-co-AAc)-ThU	17.2	[102]
P(HEMA)	27.2	[134]
P(HEMA-co-DEAE)	9.3	[141]
P(HEMA-co-PEI)	8.9	[141]
P(HEMA)/p(GMA-co-EDMA)	18.4	[141]
P(HEMA)	8.7	[141]
P(NIPA-co-MAH)	16.9	[197]
P(HEMA-co-MAGA)/p(HEMA)	29.2	[194]
P(HEMA-co-AdeM)	6.7	[195]
P(CHI-co-Q-NFC)	49.5	[198]
p(HEMA-co-GMA)	4.9	[199]
p(HEMA-co-GMA)-PEI-IIP-Cu	8.4	[200]
P(HEMA-co-MAPA)	42	[196]

Table 4

Functional groups and frequencies

Functional group	Functional group name	Type of vibration	Wavelength range, cm ⁻¹	Ref
OH	Hydroxyl group	Stretching, intra-molecular hydrogen bonds	3600-3200	[25,52]
NH ₂	Primary amine	Stretching	1690-1640	[142]
NH	Secondary amine	Bending	1650-1580	[55]
C=N	Imine	Stretching	1690-1640	[136]

C=O	Amide I	Stretching	1690-1650	[204]
C-N	Amine	Stretching	1250-1000	[204]
COOH	Carboxylic acid group	Stretching	3400-2500	[204,205]
CONH ₂	Amide II	Stretching	3500-3400, 1560-1510, 1650-1620	[136]
CONHR	Amide III	Stretching	1550-1530	[123]
C=CH ₂	Alkene	Stretching	3080, 2950	[29]
C-O	Ether	Stretching	1150-1050	[123]
C=O	Carbonyl group	Stretching	1750-1715	[25]
C-O-C	Ether	Stretching	1100	[206]
C-H	Alkyl	Stretching	3000-2850	[109]
C-H	Alkane	Bending	1390-1370, 1470-1450, 1070-1060	[52]
-SO ₃ H	Sulfur	Stretching	1070-1030, 1245-1130	[207,208]

Table 5

Literature review on heavy metals removal from water by use of cryogels

Metal	Cryogel	Main functional groups	Predominant mechanism(s)	Initial aqueous phase concentration (mg/L)	Adsorption capacity q _e (mg/g)	pH	Reference
Al(III)	p(HEMA)-P. chrysosporium		biosorption Coordination	27	2.97	6.0	[217]
Cu(II)	p(Jeff600-co-GA-co-DAH)	-NH ₂ R-COOH	Chemisorption Physisorption	100	119	5.5	[142]
	p(Jeff600-co-GA)	-NH ₂ R-COOH	Physisorption	80	55	5.5	[25]
	p(Jeff900-co-GA)	-NH ₂ R-COOH	Physisorption	80	47	5.5	[25]
	p(Jeff2003-co-GA)	-NH ₂ R-COOH	Physisorption	80	34	5.5	[25]
	p(GMA-co-His)	-OH	Coordinate-	600	5.6	5.5	[106]

		-C=O	covalent bonding				
	p(HEMA-co-VIM)/p(HEMA)	-OH - CH=CH ₂	Chelation	20	2.5	5.5	[52]
	p(CHI-co-HEMA)	-NH ₂ -OH -C=O	Chelation	100	66.3	6.0	[70]
	p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Cu	-NH ₂ -C=O -NH	Chemisorption	60	77.2	6.0	[55]
	p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Cu-Fe ₂ O ₃	-NH ₂ -C=O -NH	Chemisorption	60	182.7	6.0	[55]
	p(HEMA-co-GMA)-PEI-IIP-Cu	R-COOR -OH	Electrostatic interaction	120	1.21	5.5	[103]
	p(AA-co-MAAc-AAm)	-COOH -NH ₂ -C=O	Metal complexation	64	630	4.0	[137]
	p(HEMA)-P. chrysosporium	biosorption	Coordination	63.5	24.1	6.0	[217]
	p(PVA-co-CMC)	-OH -COOH	Ion exchange	100	5.5	-	[28]
Fe(II)	p(HEMA)-P. chrysosporium	biosorption	Coordination	55.8	5.6	6.0	[217]
UO₂(II)	p(AN)	-C≡N -CH=CH ₂	Chelation	6.8	1.8	7.8	[204]
Pb(II)	p(GMA-co-His)	-OH -C=O	Coordinate-covalent bonding	600	6.9	5.0	[106]
	p(HEMA-co-VIM)/p(HEMA)	-OH -CH=CH ₂	Chelation	20	7.6	5.5	[52]
	p(AAm)/TiO ₂	-NH ₂ -C=O	Ion exchange	100	23.3	5.5	[121]
	p(AA-co-DMAAm-co-AAc)-ThU	-COOH -NH ₂ -C=O	Ion exchange Metal complexation	400	164.3	7.0	[102]
Zn(II)	p(GMA-co-His)	-OH -C=O	Coordinate-covalent bonding	600	4.2	5.0	[106]

	p(CHI-co-HEMA)	-NH ₂ -OH -C=O	Chelation	100	57.6	6.0	[70]
	p(HEMA-co-VIM)/p(HEMA)	-OH -CH=CH ₂	Chelation	4.3	7.6	5.5	[52]
	p(PVA-co-CMC)	-OH -COOH	Ion exchange	100	5.3	-	[28]
	p(HEMA)-P. chrysosporium	biosorption	Coordination	65.4	7.85	6.0	[217]
Cd(II)	p(GMA-co-His)	-OH -C=O	Coordinate-covalent bonding	600	6.4	5.0	[106]
	p(HEMA-co-MAC)	-NH -COOH -SH -C=O	Metal complexation	100	0.52	-	[185]
	p(HEMA-co-MAC)	-NH -COOH -SH -C=O	Chemisorption	20	0.006	6.0	[123]
	p(HEMA-co-MAC)/IIP-Cd	-NH -COOH -SH -C=O	Chemisorption	20	0.032	6.0	[123]
	p(HEMA-co-MAC)/IIP-Cd	-NH -COOH -SH -C=O	Metal complexation	100	3.0	-	[185]
	p(PVA-co-HA)	-OH PO ₄	Metal complexation	100	53.2	6.0	[69]
	p(HEMA-co-VIM)/p(HEMA)	-OH -CH=CH ₂	Chelation	20	5.8	5.5	[52]
	p(AAm)/TiO ₂	-NH ₂ -C=O	-	10	11	4.0	[71]
	p(HEMA)-P. chrysosporium	biosorption	Coordination	112.4	16.8	6.0	[217]
Co(II)	p(AMPS)	SO ₃ H-	Ion exchange	500	91.7	4.0	[107]
	p(AA-co-MAAc-AAm)	-COOH	Metal	59	590	4.0	[137]

		-NH ₂ -C=O	complexation				
	p(HEMA)-P. chrysosporium	biosorption	Coordination	58.9	5.3	6.0	[217]
Ni(II)	p(AMPS)	SO ₃ H-	Ion exchange	500	84.3	4.0	[107]
	p(PVA-co-CMC)	-OH -COOH	Ion exchange	100	6.0	-	[28]
	p(AA-co-MAAc-AAm)	-COOH -NH ₂ -C=O	-	58	580	4.0	[137]
	p(IM-co-AA)	-NH ₂ =CH ₂	Metal complexation	410	3.5	5.3	[218]
	p(HEMA)-P. chrysosporium	biosorption	Coordination	58.7	12.9	6.0	[217]
Ca(II)	p(CHI-co-HEMA)	-NH ₂ -OH -C=O	Metal complexation	100	48.7	6.0	[69]
Cr(VI)	p(CHI-co-DMAEMA)/ Fe ₃ O ₄	-N-R2 -NH ₂ -OH	-	0.25	14.22	-	[206]
	p(CHI-co-VAm)/VBTACl	-NH ₂ -OH =CH ₂	Chemisorption	1000	317	5.5	[143]
	p(CHI-co-VAm)	-NH ₂ -OH =CH ₂	Chemisorption	1000	225	5.5	[143]
Cr(III)	p(HEMA)-P. chrysosporium	biosorption	Coordination	52	7.3	6.0	[217]
As(III)	p(CHI-co-DMAEMA)/ Fe ₃ O ₄	-N-R2 -NH ₂ -OH	-	0.2	11.46	-	[206]
	p(HEMA-co- PEGDA)/Fe ₂ O ₃	-COOH R-COOR -OH	Metal complexation	2	2.7	7.0	[189]
	p(HEMA-co- PEGDA)/Fe ₃ O ₄	-COOH R-COOR -OH	Metal complexation	4	3.1	7.0	[189]

	p(APTMACI)/Fe	-NH -C=O	Ionic interaction Ion exchange	100	140	-	[109]
	p(AAm)/Fe(OH) ₃ - Al(OH) ₃	-NH ₂ -C=O	Chemisorption	100	24.6	4- 11	[219]
	p(AAm)/Fe(OH) ₃ - Al(OH) ₃	-NH ₂ -C=O	Chemisorption	1	82.3	7.0	[220]
As(V)	p(AAm)/Fe	-NH ₂ -C=O	Electrostatic interaction	100	50	7.0	[56]
	p(AAm)/Fe(OH) ₃ - Al(OH) ₃	-NH ₂ -C=O	Chemisorption	1	49.6	7.0	[220]
	p(AAm-co-D ₃ AAm)/ Al ₂ O ₃	-NH ₂ -C=O	Metal complexation	5	6	7.0	[68]
	p(AAm-AA)-SH	-NH ₂ -C=O	-	60	2	7.0	[136]
	p(AAm-AA)-MIP	-NH ₂ -C=O	-	60	20.6	7.0	[136]
	p(AAm-AA)-Al-NP	-NH ₂ -C=O	-	60	20.3	7.0	[136]
	p(APTMACI)/Fe	-NH -C=O	Ionic interaction Ion exchange	400	118	9.3	[139]
Ag(I)	p(HEMA-co-MAC)IIP-Ag	-NH -COOH -SH -C=O	Ionic interaction	20	49.3	4.0	[120]
Hg(II)	PEI	-NH	Ionic interaction	100	1280	7.0	[221]
	p(HEMA)- P. chryso sporium	biosorption	Coordination	200	75.2	6.0	[217]
	p(CHI-co-PVA)	-NH ₂ -OH -C=O	Ionic interaction Ion exchange	2069	585.9	5.5	[222]

Table 6. Efficiency of the regeneration of adsorbents.

Metal	Cryogel	Metal loading (mg/g)	Recovery cycles	Desorption agent	Recovery (%)	Regeneration duration (min)	Reference
Cu(II)	p(Jeff600-co-GA)	55	3	0.01M HNO ₃	56.3	-	[25]

	p(Jeff900-co-GA)	47	3	0.01M HNO ₃	61.5	-	[25]
	p(Jeff2003-co-GA)	34	3	0.01M HNO ₃	69.2	-	[25]
	p(GMA-co-His)	5.6	5	0.01M HNO ₃	97	60	[106]
	p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Cu	77.2	5	5 M Na ₂ (EDTA)	96	180	[55]
	p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Cu-Fe ₂ O ₃	182.7	5	5M Na ₂ (EDTA)	96	180	[55]
	p(HEMA-co-GMA)-PEI-IIP-Cu	1.21	5	HNO ₃	97	-	[103]
Pb(II)	p(GMA-co-His)	6.9	5	HNO ₃	97	60	[106]
Zn(II)	p(GMA-co-His)	4.2	5	HNO ₃	97	60	[106]
Cd(II)	p(GMA-co-His)	6.4	5	HNO ₃	97	60	[106]
	p(HEMA-co-MAC)	0.006	10	0.1M HNO ₃	74.4	120	[123]
	p(HEMA-co-MAC)/IIP-Cd	0.032	10	0.1M HNO ₃	84.1	120	[123]
Ag(I)	p(HEMA-co-MAC)IIP-Ag	49.3	1	0.1 M EDTA	72.8	120	[120]

Fig. 1. Cryogels prepared in different formats [Reprinted with permission from Ref. [122]. Copyright 2008, Elsevier]

Fig 2. Picture of the plastic Kaldnes carriers (A) and (B), macroporous gels formed inside the carriers (C) and SEM image of formed macroporous gel (D). [Reprinted with permission from Ref. [124]. Copyright 2008, American Chemical Society]

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the formation of cryogels

Fig. 4. Representation of the formation of 3D polymeric network under cryoconditions via different cross-linking processes: a) radical polymerization [180]; b) polycondensation reactions between polymers [181]; c) covalent cross-linking and electrostatic interactions between polymers [131]; d) non covalent cross-linking of CHI by formation metal-polymer coordination bonds [156]. [Reprinted with permission from Ref. [181], [131], [156]. Copyright 2014, Springer Nature. Copyright 2008, Elsevier. Copyright 2004, Elsevier.]

Fig. 5. The formation of the macroporous structure of polyacrylamide cryogel by time [50]

Fig. 6. The geometrically optimized by Avogadro program molecular structures of (A) p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP-Ni(II) (1:1) and (B) p(HEMA-co-MAH)/IIP -Ni (2:1) [Reprinted with permission from Ref. [192]. Copyright 2017, Elsevier]

Fig. 7. FT-IT spectra of p(MAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) cryogel .

Fig. 8. FTIR spectra of (A) p(HEMA) cryogel, (B) p(HEMA-co-VIM) cryogel and (C) p(HEMA-co-VIM)/p(HEMA) composite cryogel [Reprinted with permission from Ref. [52]. Copyright 2011, Elsevier]

Fig. 9. Graph of determination of IEP of (A) p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) and (B) parent and modified p(CHI-co-VAm) cryogels. Adapted from [29] and [143]

Fig. 10. Dependence of the flow rate on the removal of (left) Fe(III) [57] and (right) Cd(II) [185] ions by different cryogels [adapted from Ref. [57] and [185].

Fig. 11. Water uptake of 0.1 % crosslinked p(AMPS) hydrogel (a) and 10 % crosslinked p(AMPS) cryogel during the time [Reprinted with permission from Ref. [107]. Copyright 2014, The Royal Society of Chemistry]

Fig. 12. 3D plots presenting A: gel percentage B: adsorption capacity for different crosslinker and chain extender ratios [Reprinted with permission from Ref. [142]. Copyright 2017, Elsevier]

Fig. 13. Swelling degree of CHI-[PdCl₄]⁻² cryogels vs time: Pd-0.2 mM (triangle), Pd-0.4 mM (square), Pd-0.8 mM (rhomb), respectively prepared in 0.2 M acetic acid (m/mo: mass of swollen cryogel over initial mass).

Fig. 14. Optical microscopy microphotographs (A, B, C) and SEM microphotographs (D, E, F) of p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) at different magnifications with scale bar: A) 500 μm, B) 200 μm, C) 100 μm, D) 200 μm, E) 80 μm, F) 30 μm.

Fig. 15. TEM images of (a) initial p(AAm) and (b, c) modified p(AAm)/Fe-Al₂O₃ cryogels at different magnifications with scale bar: A) 500 nm, B) 100 nm, C) 100 nm [Reprinted with permission from Ref. [68]. Copyright 2014, Elsevier]

Fig. 16. TEM image of p(MAAc-co-AA-co-DMAAm) modified by AgNP (scale bar: 500 nm left, 50 nm right).

Fig. 17. Representative stress-strain curves of equilibrium-swollen MMCs cryogels prepared from CHI dissolved in HCl and composed of [PdCl₄]⁻²: 200 uM Pd (square); 400 uM Pd (triangle); 800 uM Pd (circle) [215]

Fig.18. Schematically representation of metal-polymer complexes in cryogel pores [modified and adapted from Ref. [137]].

Fig. 19. Reaction of Hg(II) ions with amino group (adapted from [221])

Fig. 20. Possible ion-exchange and chelation of metal ions with carboxylic groups [adapted from Ref. [224]]

Fig. 21. Adsorption of Cu(II) (left) and Pb(II) ions by p(Jeff600-co-GA-co-DAH) [142] and p(AA-co-DMAAm-co-AAc)-ThU [102] cryogels in different pH, respectively.

Fig. 22. Water phase speciation of Cu(NO₃)₂ (upper) and Pb(NO₃)₂ (lower) solutions (right). Graphs created on Medusa speciation software.

Beads

Sheets

Monoliths/discs

1 - Polymerization of precursors and freezing of solvent below freezing point
 2 - Thawing of the solvent

ION EXCHANGE:

CHELATION:

